

The Changing Buying Behaviour & Customer Satisfaction in Organized Retail Sector of Pune City

**A
THESIS**

**SUBMITTED TO
THE GLOBAL OPEN UNIVERSITY,
NAGALAND**

**FOR THE AWARD OF THE DEGREE OF
MASTER OF PHILOSOPHY (M.Phil.)**

**IN
MANAGEMENT**

**SUBMITTED BY
ATUL KUMAR
(Roll No: M.Phil./5237/MBA/2008D)**

**UNDER THE SUPERVISION OF
DR. PRADEEP KUMAR SINHA**

**THE GLOBAL OPEN UNIVERSITY
OPPOSITE RAILWAY STATION, DIMAPUR,
PIN- 797112, NAGALAND (INDIA)
(2010-11)**

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Mr. Atul Kumar** registered himself as a candidate for research work leading to M.Phil. on the subject “**The Changing Buying Behaviour & Customer Satisfaction in Organized Retail Sector of Pune City**”.

He did the entire work under my supervision. This thesis is an original work and he has done his research work to my satisfaction.

The study is based on the investigations made by the candidate and its contents do not form a part of any other research work on similar lines in India. The thesis is in my opinion complete and suitable for the award of M.Phil. degree.

I recommend that this thesis be accepted for submission in The Global Open University, Dimapur- 797112, Nagaland (India) for the award of master of philosophy (M.Phil.) in Management.

Nagaland

Dr. Pradeep Kumar Sinha
Supervisor

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the research work as submitted through this thesis entitled “The Changing Buying Behaviour & Customer Satisfaction in Organized Retail Sector of Pune City” has been carried out by me under supervision of **Dr. Pradeep Kumar Sinha**.

The work is of original nature. To the best of my knowledge, no such study has been previously done on the lines of this thesis in India.

Nagaland

ATUL KUMAR
Research Scholar

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I acknowledge my gratitude with sense of reverence to the *Almighty God* and those who have contributed and spared time for the completion of this thesis. Their valuable guidance and wise direction has enabled me to complete my thesis in a systematic way.

At the outset, my ethical accountability is to be extremely indebted to **Prof. (Dr.) Priya Ranjan Trivedi**, Pro Chancellor, The Global Open University, Dimapur- 797112, Nagaland (India) for his gracious permission to carry out this work.

In an ecstasy of delight, I express my profound sense of gratitude to my esteemed guide and supervisor, **Dr. Pradeep Kumar Sinha**, Director, Zeal Education Society's Dyanganga Institute of Management & Computer Application, Pune (Maharashtra), for his scholarly, inspiring supervision, incessant painstaking efforts and stimulating guidance patronage. He persevered beyond my expectations. Without his careful guidance and useful advices, the accomplishments in this thesis would not be possible.

I am thankful to **Dr. T. R. Sontakke**, Principal, Siddhant College of Engineering, Pune for his help and support.

I would like to acknowledge **Dr. V. O. Varkey**, Director, Siddhant Group of Institutions, Pune for his encouraging support and valuable suggestions on various occasions in giving final shape to this work.

I would like to acknowledge the significant contributions to this work made by **Dr. Vinaydeep Brar**, *Assistant Professor*, Siddhant Group of Institutions, Pune. He played equally important and complimentary role in shaping the work reported in this thesis.

I am thankful to **Dr. B. R. Ranwah**, Associate Professor, Department of Plant Breeding and Genetics, Rajasthan Agriculture University, Udaipur for his cooperation in statistical analysis.

I also acknowledge my parents who provided moral support to make it possible for me to pursue this goal.

It is also my deem duty to express my gratefulness to each and every person of various retailers, who extended me their help to make this thesis work a successful venture.

The incredible help offered by rest of the persons whose names could not be mentioned, is incomparable and deserve the highest degree of appreciation.

ATUL KUMAR
Research Scholar

CONTENTS

Certificates	
Acknowledgement	
Chapter 1. Introduction	
Chapter 2. Review of Literature	
Chapter 3. Research Methodology	
Chapter 4. Results and Discussions	
• Section I: Descriptive Analysis of Demographic & Geographic Variables of Customers of Organized Retailers	
• Section II: Descriptive Analysis of Behavioural Characteristics (Changing Buying Behaviour) of Customers of Organized Retailers	
• Section III: Descriptive Analysis of Preference of Customers of Organized Retailers	
• Section IV: Analysis of Influences of Factors Affecting Buying Behaviour (Buying Decisions)	
• Section V: Analysis of Satisfaction Level of Customers of Organized Retailers	
Chapter 5. Conclusions and Recommendations	
Chapter 6. Appendix I: Individual Questionnaire	
Chapter 7. Bibliography	

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

In India, organized retail sector has been modernized, growing at much faster rate, contributing to country's GDP and providing employment. Apart from that organized retailers are providing better shopping experience to Indian consumers in terms of quality service, quality products, product assortment, and pleasant ambience etc.

Organized retail sector is facing lot of challenges like poor infrastructure and technology, less smooth supply chain, untrained human resource, government restrictions on foreign direct investment etc.

The future of organized retailing in India is bright. McKinsey Global Institute, in association with Indian Council for Research on International Economic Relation (ICRIER) brought out a study report titled "The bird of gold: The rise of Indian consumer market". This states the rise of Indian consumer market and its influences on consumer spending and their behaviour.¹

ORGANIZED RETAILING IN INDIA- FACTS AND FIGURES

This concept of organized retailing in India emerged in the 70's, when some shoppers like Bata, and Raymond established their stores and franchises for the business directly with the customers.

In 80's Spencer's appeared in Chennai and Akbarally's appeared in Mumbai afterward spread into multi chain outlets and strongly established the concept of organized retailing in India.

Because of Liberalization, privatization, and globalization (LPG) of Indian economy during 90's, this contemporary concept of retailing is generated by some retailer like Shoppers Stop in 1991 and Pantaloon in 1997 but in the end of 20th century, Indian market were witness of huge changes in the organized retail industry in terms of their format.

During that period many supermarkets, hypermarkets, chain stores, discount stores, and departmental stores came into existence and now in 2010 organized retailing is booming in India.

Minister of state for commerce of India discusses a study conducted by ICRIER, which states that Indian retail trade industry will grow 10% per annum.

And organized retail trade segment, which presently stands at just 4% (December 2008) will grow a much faster pace of 45%-50% to grab a 16% share of the market by 2011-12.²

Indian retail sector is contributing 10% to country's GDP and also providing 8% employment, which is highest after agriculture.³

Even though, Indian retail sector is highly dominated by unorganized retails like-

- Local grocery shops,
- Owner managed general stores,
- Chemist and druggist stores,
- Apparel stores,
- Footwear stores,
- Hand cart hawkers,
- Local venders,
- Kiosks etc.

Still organized retail segments' sales grew 20% per annum which is much greater than total sales growth of retail sector i.e. 11%. And share of organized retail is also growing slowly from 3.3 in 2003-04 to 4.1% in 2006-07 (Exhibit 1).

Main drivers to get the growth in the retail sector of India-

- Food and grocery,
- Clothing and footwear,
- Non-institutional healthcare,
- Furnishing appliances and services,
- Jewelry and
- Watches (Exhibit 2 and 3).

Exhibit 1: Share of organized retail in total retail sales (Sales Rs. bn)

Year	2003-04	2004-05	2005-06	2006-07
Total retail sales	10,591	11,308	12,023	14,574
Total contribution of organized retail trade	352	415	479	598
Share of organized retail (%)	3.3	3.7	4.0	4.1
Source: Technopak Advisors Pvt. Ltd. ⁴				

The growth in the Indian organized retail market is mainly due to the change in the consumer's behavior.

This change has come in the consumer due to-

- Increased income,
- Changing lifestyle,
- Patterns of demography which are favorable,

- Western influences,
- Desire for luxury, and
- Better quality.

Other main factors responsible for rapid growth of retail trade industry in India are-

- Increase in literacy rate,
- Working women population,
- Better economic situation of family,
- Entry of new big players in this retail sector,
- Increased customer services-orientation,
- Low cost labor & raw materials and
- Ample scope for FDI.

Exhibit 2: Growth of Indian Retail Sector (Sales Rs. bn)

Year	2003-04	2004-05	2005-06	2006-07
Food and Grocery	7,028	7,064	7,418	8,680
Clothing and Footwear	777	993	1,036	1,356
Jewelry and Watches	530	610	655	863
Personal Care	371	433	465	617
Beverages	212	309	373	518
Furnishing Appliances and Services	512	656	746	986
Sport Goods, Entertainment Equipments & Books	212	272	308	395
Non-Institutional Healthcare	950	972	1,022	1,150
Source: Technopak Advisors Pvt. Ltd. ⁵				

Exhibit 3: Growth of Indian Organized Retail Sector (Sales Rs. bn)

Year	2003-04	2004-05	2005-06	2006-07
Food and Grocery	39	44	50	61
Clothing and Footwear	168	189	212	251
Jewelry and Watches	18	24	33	49
Personal Care	11	15	22	33
Beverages	11	12	13	16
Furnishing Appliances and Services	67	75	85	101
Sport Goods, Entertainment Equipments & Books	25	33	44	63
Non-Institutional Healthcare	14	16	19	24
Source: Technopak Advisors Pvt. Ltd. ⁶				

Indian organized retail sector is facing a lot of challenges which are stopping Indian retail industry from reaching its full potential. The behavior pattern of the Indian consumer has undergone a major change.

Consumer now wants to eat, shop, and get entertained under the same roof. All these have lead the Indian organized retail sector to give more in order to satisfy the Indian customers.

The biggest challenge, Indian organized retail sector facing, is the lack of retail space. There are 12 million retail outlets in India, surviving in size less than 500 Sq. Ft.⁷.

With real estate prices escalating due to increase in demand from the Indian organized retail sector, it is posing a challenge to its growth. Indian retailers have to shell out more for retail space.

It is affecting overall profitability in retail. Trained manpower shortage is also a challenge that organized retail sector is facing in India. The Indian retailers have difficulty in finding trained person and also have to pay more in order to retain them.

The Indian government has allowed 51% foreign direct investment (FDI) in the Indian retail sector to one brand shops only. Government of India has no future plan to open retail sector to foreign direct investment.

In a written reply in the Rajya Sabha (Parliament of India), the minister of state for commerce of India said “the government fully recognizes the need to insure that small retailers are not adversely affected by growing organized retail and there is no adverse effect on employment”.⁸ This has made the entry of global retail giants to organized retail sector in India difficult.

The scope of the Indian retail market has been seen by many retail giants therefore many new players are entering in the Indian retail industry. The global retail giants like Tesco, Wal-Mart, and Metro AG are entering in organized retail sector of India indirectly through franchisee agreement and “cash and carry” wholesale trading.

Many Indian companies are also entering in Indian organized retail sector like-

- Reliance Industries Limited,
- Bharti Telecoms,
- Pantaloons Retail India Ltd.,
- Shoppers Stop,

- Bata India Ltd., and
- Music World Entertainment Limited.

The scope for growth in the Indian retail market is seen mainly in the following cities of India:

- Mumbai,
- Delhi,
- Pune,
- Ahmedabad,
- Bangalore,
- Hyderabad,
- Kolkata, and
- Chennai.

-
1. [http:// www.mckinsey.com/mgi/publications/india_consumer_market/executive_summary.asp](http://www.mckinsey.com/mgi/publications/india_consumer_market/executive_summary.asp)
 2. Marketing Mastermind, September 2009, ICFAI University Press, India, pp.- 7.
 3. [http:// www.business.mapsofindia.com/indian-retail-industry/](http://www.business.mapsofindia.com/indian-retail-industry/)
 4. [http:// www.technopak.com/vertical/retail.asp](http://www.technopak.com/vertical/retail.asp)
 5. [http:// www.technopak.com/vertical/retail.asp](http://www.technopak.com/vertical/retail.asp)
 6. [http:// www.technopak.com/vertical/retail.asp](http://www.technopak.com/vertical/retail.asp)
 7. <http://www.ibid.informindia.co.in>
 8. Marketing Mastermind, September 2009, ICFAI University Press, India, pp.- 7.
-

OBJECTIVES

- To study various demographic & geographic variables of customers of organized retailers.
- To study the changing buying behavior of customers of organized retailers.
- To know the preference of customers while purchase making decisions.
- To analyze the influence level of factors affecting buying behavior.
- To evaluate the satisfaction level of customers with regards to various services rendered by organized retailers in Pune city.

RATIONALE BEHIND THE STUDY

As we know, retailing is an industry which drives a major part of its revenue from direct transaction with final consumers. This revenue generated by the sale and sale relies upon the consumer behavior.

Consumer behavior is highly affected by customer satisfaction. If consumer is satisfied, he/she will not only be loyal but also spared a positive word of mouth. Customer satisfaction is also remedy to retain customers, stimulate sales, revenue and profit, and attach customers psychologically and emotionally.

This study is confined with the two retailers named as Big Bazaar (Pantaloon Retail India Ltd.) and D'Mart (Avenue Super Market Pvt. Ltd.). Big Bazaar is well known brand in retailing all over India. But business of D'Mart is only in state of Maharashtra. Both retailers offer a wide range of products and services to customers.

CHAPTER 2

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

BUYING BEHAVIOR

Customer loyalty sometimes has been identified as a behavioral measure and at other times as an attitude. Behavioral measures include repeat purchase behavior (Brown, 1952), probability of purchase (Farley, 1964), purchase frequency (Brody and Cunningham, 1968).

Enis and Paul (1970) indicated that loyalty is symbol of poor shoppers, But McGoldrick et al. (1997) found in their study income and weekly expenditures of loyal customers are significantly higher.

Popai/Du Pont (1977) studied out that mostly consumer's purchase decisions are taken in stores due to retail forces, manufacturer forces, and word of mouth forces etc.

Mayer (1989) suggested that store image has been one of the main topics in retailing.

Pan and Zinkhan (2006) in their study "Determinants of retail patronage: a metaanalytical perspective" claimed that store image and attributes strongly affects the store visit frequency.

Kelly et al. (1993) noticed that a service encounter failure is the main cause to lose customers in retail outlets.

Russo and France (1994) studied the attitude of the choice process for commonly purchased non-durables by tracking eye fixations in a laboratory simulation of super

market shelves. Their finding indicated that the choice process is constructed to adapt to the immediate purchase environment.

Consumers choose product and service on the basis of a combination of product attributes meeting their needs on the dimensions of value, cost and satisfaction in the best way (Kotler, 1997).

Strugnell (1997) focused on Irish consumers as to why they are becoming more accustomed to ethnic cuisine although traditional meals are popular. It was found that consumption of these products is higher in Ireland than in the UK main land.

The products are often purchased as a convenient alternative or a weekly treat. Customer behavior is affected by customer satisfaction and switchy barrier. (Gerpott et al., 2001).

Maison et al. (2001) pointed out in the mid of 20th century, consumer choose the product and service consciously and rationally.

Broadbride and Calderwood (2002) studied the fact that to survive in the increased competitions from organized retailers, local shops have to focus on needs and wants of local customer with the commitment and willingness to cater them.

Rodriguez et al. (2002) explained about Argentinean consumers' behavior that they are less likely to buy fresh fruit and vegetables, red meat and bread at a super market. They would rather buy these things from shop offering personal attention and services for those products.

Indian shoppers seek emotional value than on the functional value and are affected primarily by the type of store, the frequency of buying and to some extent, by the socio-economic classification. The retailers need to experiment with a format that attracts both types of shopper reported by Sinha (2003).

Knox and Walker (2003) found that there is a significant relationship between involvement and brand loyalty in grocery markets.

Sinha and Banerjee (2004) studied store choice behavior and carried out that proximity to residence and comfort level are major factors to visit outlets.

Hyllegard et al. (2005) analyzed Spanish consumer's perceptions of US apparel specialty retailer's product and services and find out that perception differs from person to person with regard to quality of product and service and their assortment.

Sukalakamala, Boyce (2005) investigated customer's perception, acceptance, expectations, and the importance of knowing consumer perception and observed that demand estimation is essential for success.

Yuping (2007) examined long term impact on loyalty programs on consumer purchase behavior and loyalty. Study resulted loyalty programs did not temp consumers to change their purchase behavior.

Tarun and Chopra (2007) analyzed that Indian retailers understand the culture, taste and preference of Indian consumer better and Indian consumer is also known to be extremely value-conscious.

Indian consumers are price sensitive and because of that retails work with them on low profit margin, argued by Vijayraghavan (2007).

Fraj and Martinez (2007) focused on environment and natural attitudes predicator of ecological behavior of consumers and showed that environmental attitudes have an important influence on ecological behavior.

In a study of impact of demographic variables on consumer preference for the cosmetic products Parmar and Gupta (2007) found that age, occupation, family income have

significant influence on the selection of products. Further, it was also found that brand loyalty does not have a significant influence on the buying behavior of consumers when brand of their choice is not available.

Indian customers have become more sensitive to quality, customer service and status. They are basically looking for an experience which is more cognitive than physical, suggested by Pathak and Tripathi (2009).

Harish and Suchitra (2010) explained that sales promotion entice consumer buying behavior in organized retailing.

CUSTOMER SATISFACTION

In a study of product performance and customer satisfaction, Swan and Combs (1976) found a positive relation between customer satisfaction and product performance, dimensions of which were categorized qualitatively into instrumental and expressive. Instrumental comprises natural attributes of the product line capability; usability etc. and expressive comprises psychological or determinant attributes like color, style etc.

“Customer satisfaction is a summary of psychological state when the emotions surroundings disconfirmed expectations are coupled with the consumer’s prior feelings about consumption experience.” (Oliver, 1980)

It was later identified by Oliver (1981) that the distribution channels are unique role players in satisfying the needs of the retailer and manufacturer by proposing a non-traditional multiphase satisfaction program based on major components of satisfaction process.

Churchill and Surprenant (1982) defined that “customer satisfaction is amount but, resulting from the customer’s pre-purchase comparison of expected performance with perceived actual performance and incurred cost.”

Customer satisfaction is an important tool that can increase profit by preventing customers from defecting (Reichheld and Sasser 1990).

Yi (1991) in a critical review of customer satisfaction argued that customer satisfaction operates in two different ways: transaction-specific and general overall. The transaction-specific concept concerns customer satisfaction as the assessment made after a specific purchase.

Overall satisfaction refers to how the customers rate the brand, based on all encounters and experience. (Johnson and Fornell, 1991)

It is resulted out in the study of Fornell (1992) that customer satisfaction increase customer loyalty and prevents customer churn, lowers the customers price sensitivity, reduces the costs of failed marketing and of new customer creation, reduces operating costs due to the increase in the number of customers, improves the effectiveness of the advertising and enhances business reputation.

Attitudinal approaches are focused mainly on repurchase intention (Anderson and Sullivan, 1993) and resistance to superior products (Narayandas, 1996).

Parasuraman et al. (1994) suggested a simple and clear definition for satisfaction that “satisfaction is influenced by service quality, product quality and price.”

Haemoun Oh (1999) suggested a model for customer satisfaction which appears to possess practical validity as well as explanatory ability. He used this model in hotel industry, and results are supporting a holistic approach to hospitality of customers post purchase decision-making process.

Customer satisfaction has a positive impact on customer retention; thereby implying that the customer satisfaction has a positive effect on loyalty, concluded by Bei and Chiao (2001).

Miranda et al. (2005) confirmed that overall satisfaction from store did not affect the customer loyalty. It is affected by several reasons such as- frequently buyer reward schemes, travel distance, preference for an in-store delicatessen, size of the average grocery bill, store signage and level of sale assistance.

Goswami and Mishra (2007) found that customer loyalty and satisfaction is positively related to location, cleanliness, quality, offers, helpful, trustworthy salespeople, home shopping etc and negatively related to travel inconvenience.

CHAPTER 3

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter on methodology gives the description of research procedure followed to carry out the present study. The literature surveyed proves vehemently that individual response has been studied. The detailed research methodology of the present work is being presented under following heads:

Research Approach

The study was based on both exploratory and descriptive research, while exploratory research helped in developing the hypotheses through the analysis of secondary data, descriptive research was used in order to study the changing buying behavior and customer satisfaction.

DATA SOURCE

Collection of Data

Both primary and secondary data were used in compiling this whole study, secondary data played a vital role to review of literature, formulate hypothesis and questionnaire. It was accumulated from books, journals, magazines, websites and other published sources available.

Selection of Tools

To accumulate the primary data, utilizing the information from the secondary data, a questionnaire was prepared to complete this study.

Pilot Study

This questionnaire was tested by conducting a pilot study of a few customers selected on random basis. Utilizing the insight from pilot study, questionnaire was modified for the final study. This primary data was accumulated from customers of two organized retailers named as Big Bazaar and D'Mart.

Method of Data Collection

Survey method was employed to carry out this study through printed questionnaires by a personal interview technique.

Scales

Nominal and ordinal scales were utilized to take the responses regarding demographic and geographic variables, changing buying behavior, factors affecting buying behavior, and satisfaction level of customers.

Tabulation

One way tabulation has been utilized to represent the demographic and geographic variables, responses regarding changing buying behavior and cross tabulation to present the preferences of customers while making purchase decisions.

SAMPLING PLAN

Locale of the Study

This study was confined only with the Pune district of Maharashtra State (India).

Sample Size

The questionnaires were distributed simultaneously among 400 respondents during September-October 2009, in which 200 questionnaire were filled by Big Bazaar's customers and rest of 200 by customers of D'Mart.

Organized Retailer	Respondents
Big Bazaar	200
D'Mart	200
<hr/>	
Total	400
<hr/>	

Sampling Procedure

Survey was done in all seven days but in Big Bazaar, we specially surveyed on Wednesday as well as in other days also due to special schemes and discounts provided by Big Bazaar on this day of the week. This day is declared as a SABSE SASTA DIN (Lowest pricing day).

Sampling Technique

Customers of organized retailers were selected on random basis from their customers when they visited stores on week days. For the purpose of this survey, Random Sampling of Probability Sampling Technique has been employed as it gives every unit of the population a known and non-zero probability of being selected.

ANALYSIS OF DATA

Percentage:

Simple percentage method has been used to analyze the demographic and geographic variables, responses regarding changing buying behavior and preferences of customers while making purchase decisions.

Kolmogorov-Smirnov One Sample test

This test has been applied to test the hypothesis.

Standardization of Scale

It was standardized by Spearman Brown Prophecy formula for reliability and the same was validated by computing index of reliability.

Reliability of the Scale

Reliability of the scale was drawn by split half method.

The scale was given to a group of 100 subjects. In split-half technique, the test was first divided into two equal halves and correlation between these half tests was computed. From the correlation coefficient of the half tests the self-correlation of the whole test was estimated by using Karl Pearson formula.

In split half technique, the test was first divided into two equal halves and correlation between these half tests was computed.

From the correlation coefficient of the half tests- the self correlation of the whole test was estimated by using Karl Pearson Formula-

$$r = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n X_i Y_i - \frac{\left[\sum_{i=1}^n X_i \right] \left[\sum_{i=1}^n Y_i \right]}{n}}{\sqrt{\left[\sum_{i=1}^n X_i^2 - \frac{\left[\sum_{i=1}^n X_i \right]^2}{n} \right] \left[\sum_{i=1}^n Y_i^2 - \frac{\left[\sum_{i=1}^n Y_i \right]^2}{n} \right]}}$$

For Split half technique-

X_i and Y_i = were the two variables in each case.

$\sum X_i Y_i$ = Sum total of products of the raw scores.

$\sum X_i^2$ and $\sum Y_i^2$	=	Sum total of squares of X_i and Y_i
n	=	Total number of subjects
r	=	Correlation co-efficient

In test retest method, correlation was found between scores of first test, and scores of second test by using the same formula of Karl Pearson.

Reliability coefficient of the whole test is estimated by Spearman Brown Prophecy formula-

$$r_{II} = \frac{2r^{1/2}I/II}{1 + r^{1/2}I/II}$$

Where r_{II} = reliability coefficient of whole test in split half technique.
 = reliability coefficient of the half test in split half technique.

Spearman Brown Prophecy formula was used for estimating reliability coefficient from two comparable values of split-half technique and test-retest method.

Intrinsic validity of the scale:

Intrinsic validity is calculated by the formula of Index of reliability

For split half technique:

$$r_{1\alpha} = \sqrt{r_{II}}$$

The ‘index of reliability’ of scores was also calculated. The correlation between the set of obtained scores and their corresponding true counter parts was given by the formula-

For split half techniques-

$r_{1\alpha}$ = Index of reliability

r_{II} = the reliability coefficient of whole test

Validity of the scale

The validity of the scale was assessed by way of measuring the content concurrent and intrinsic validity of the scale. The validation of the content, through competent judgment, was most satisfactory where the sampling of items was wide and judicious and when adequate standardization groups were utilized.

Validity was assessed by using formula of index of reliability, which is known as intrinsic validity. The index of reliability is sometimes taken as measure of validity. A highly reliable test is always a valid measure of some function. The correlation gave the relationship between obtained scores and their theoretical true counter parts.

HYPOTHESIS

- There is no significant influence of factors on buying decisions.
- There is no significant satisfaction among customers with regards to various services rendered by organized retailers in Pune.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

- This study was limited to few customers selected on random basis of organized retailers named as: Big Bazaar and D'Mart.
- For want of time and resources study also was confined to only selected regions.
- Frauds/fault in giving the right information may not be neglected.

IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

- This study furnishes information about- various demographic and geographic variables of customers.

- This study also furnishes information about
 - Changing buying behavior,
 - Factors influencing buying behavior,
 - Customer preference and
 - Customer satisfaction level with regards to different products and services offered by organized retailers.

- Study also highlights the problems of customers and their possible solutions.

- Study put some light on improvements required in the products and services provided by organized retailers.

- The study helps the responsible management of organized retailers to formulate more effective strategies to attract new customers and to increase the satisfaction level of existing customers.

- The study will further prove to be great help to the researchers/management students who want to do similar or related study in the future.

CHAPTER 4

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This chapter consists of the analysis of the various data, which have been collected through a set of questionnaires. In later parts of the chapter, results have been interpreted and discussed to reach on some inferences. Chapter has been divided into various sections as follows:

The whole study is divided into five main headings according to objectives of the study.

Section I

Descriptive Analysis of Demographic & Geographic Variables of Customers of Organized Retailers

Section II

Descriptive Analysis of Behavioural Characteristics (Changing Buying Behaviour) of Customers of Organized Retailers

Section III

Descriptive Analysis of Preference of Customers of Organized Retailers

Section IV

Analysis of Influences of Factors Affecting Buying Behaviour (Buying Decisions)

Section V

Analysis of Satisfaction Level of Customers of Organized Retailers

RESULTS

SECTION I

DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS OF DEMOGRAPHIC & GEOGRAPHIC VARIABLES OF CUSTOMERS OF ORGANIZED RETAILERS

1. Gender Analysis of Customers

Variable	Sub-Variable	Frequency
Gender	Male	238
	Female	162

2. Age Analysis of Customers

Variable	Sub-Variable	Percentage (%)
Age (Years)	< 15	04.00
	16-30	39.75
	31-45	26.00
	46-60	22.50
	> 60	07.75

3. Marital Status Analysis of Customers

Variable	Sub-Variable	Frequency
Marital Status	Single	96
	Married	304

4. Education Status Analysis of Customers

Variable	Sub-Variable	Percentage (%)
Educational Status	Illiterate	07.00
	Below 10th	07.75
	10th to 12th	13.25
	Graduation	33.00
	Post Graduation	39.00

5. Working Nature Analysis of Customers

Variable	Sub-Variable	Frequency
Working Nature	Yes	287
	No	113

6. Occupation Status Analysis

Variable	Sub-Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Occupation Status	Student	49	12.25
	Salaried	175	43.75
	Own Business	112	28.00
	House Wife	43	10.75
	Retired	21	05.25

7. Income Analysis of Customers

Variable	Sub-Variable	Percentage (%)
Household Income (Yearly) in Indian National Rupee (INR)	< 1 Lakh	13.25
	1 - 2 Lakhs	24.50
	2 - 5 Lakhs	45.75
	> 5 Lakhs	16.50

8. Family' Nature Analysis of Customers

Variable	Sub-Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Nature of Family	Nuclear	313	78.25
	Joint	87	21.75

9. Family Size Analysis of Customers

Variable	Sub-Variable	Percentage (%)
Family Size	2 -3 Members	35.50
	4-5 Members	32.25
	6-7 Members	21.25
	> 7 Members	11.00

10. Residing Area Analysis of Customers

Variable	Sub-Variable	Percentage (%)
Residing Area	Urban	74.00
	Rural	26.00

11. Gender and Working Nature Analysis

SECTION II

DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS OF BEHAVIOURAL CHARACTERISTICS (CHANGING BUYING BEHAVIOUR) OF CUSTOMERS OF ORGANIZED RETAILERS

1. Purchase Making decision of the Family

Characteristics	Sub-Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Purchase Making decision of the Family Taken	Self	239	59.75
	Others	161	40.25

2. Purchase Making Decision & Gender Analysis

3. Nature of Information Collection Decision while a Purchase Making Decision

Characteristics	Sub-Characteristics	Frequency
Information Collection Decision	Yes	288
	No	112

4. Purchasing for the Family Done

Characteristics	Sub-Characteristics	Percentage (%)
Purchasing done by	Self	71.50
	Others	28.50

5. Association with Retail Outlet

Characteristics	Sub-Characteristics	Percentage (%)
Time Period of visiting outlet	First Time	05.00
	Last 6 months	12.25
	Last one year	14.75
	Last two year	16.00
	> Two year	52.00

6. Retail Outlets Visiting Behaviour

Characteristics	Sub-Characteristics	Percentage (%)
Frequency to visit outlet (Monthly)	1 Time	15.25
	2 Times	26.75
	3 Times	06.25
	4 Times	17.00
	> 4 times	34.75

7. Preferential Day for Visiting Outlet

Characteristics	Sub-Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Day preference to visit outlet	Monday-Tuesday	6	01.50
	Wednesday	69	17.25
	Thursday-Friday	11	02.75
	Saturday-Sunday	281	70.25
	Any Day	33	08.25

8. Preferential Time for Visiting Outlet

Characteristics	Sub-Characteristics	Percentage (%)
Time Preference to visit outlet	Morning	03.00
	Afternoon	05.75
	Evening	71.25
	Any Time	20.00

9. Money Spending Behaviour

Characteristics	Sub-Characteristics	Percentage (%)
Money Spend (Monthly)	< Rs. 1000	13.75
	Rs. 1000-2000	24.25
	Rs. 2001-5000	36.25
	> Rs. 5000	25.75

10. Sources of influencing Buying Decisions

Characteristics	Sub-Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Sources of Influencing Buying Decision	Self	139	34.75
	Family Members	289	72.25
	Neighbors/Friends/Relatives	235	58.75
	Advertising	132	33.00
	Others	59	14.75

11. Sources of Information Collection while Making Purchase Decisions

Characteristics	Sub-Characteristics	Percentage (Out of 100 %)
Sources of Information Collection	Advertising	54.50
	Family Members	50.25
	Neighbors/Friends/Relatives	48.00
	Others	16.75

12. Nature of Information Collection & Sources of Information

13. Product Purchasing Behaviour

Characteristics	Sub-Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Types of Products Purchased	Food and Grocery	130	32.50
	Apparel	122	30.50
	Consumer Durables	37	09.25
	Others	81	20.25
	All	218	54.50

14. Reasons for Selection of Outlet

Characteristics	Sub-Characteristics	Percentage (Out of 100%)
Reasons to visit outlet	Proximity to home/office	79.50
	Variety of products	93.25
	Reasonable prices	35.50
	Discount & special schemes	77.50
	Good customer services	48.50
	Good & spacious ambience	35.75
	Behavior of employees	42.25
	Billing through plastic money	51.75

15. Customers Visiting more than one Outlet & Reason for Visiting more than one Outlet

SECTION III

DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS OF PREFERENCE OF CUSTOMERS OF ORGANIZED RETAILERS

1. Brand Preference of Customers while Purchase Making Decisions

Preference	Brand	
	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1 st	99	24.75
2 nd	114	28.50
3 rd	85	21.25
4 th	62	15.50
5 th	40	10.00
Total	400	100

2. Quality Preference of Customers while Purchase Making Decisions

Preference	Quality	
	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1 st	165	41.25
2 nd	90	22.50
3 rd	67	16.75
4 th	41	10.25
5 th	37	9.25
Total	400	100

3. Price Preference of Customers while Purchase Making Decisions

Preference	Price	
	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1 st	68	17.00
2 nd	105	26.25
3 rd	127	31.75
4 th	51	12.75
5 th	49	12.25
Total	400	100

4. Discount/Schemes Preference of Customers while Purchase Making Decisions

Preference	Discount/Schemes	
	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1 st	62	15.50
2 nd	73	18.25
3 rd	89	22.25
4 th	90	22.50
5 th	86	21.50
Total	400	100

5. Other Preference of Customers while Purchase Making Decisions

Preference	Others	
	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1 st	06	01.50
2 nd	18	04.50
3 rd	32	08.00
4 th	156	39.00
5 th	188	47.00
Total	400	100

SECTION IV

ANALYSIS OF INFLUENCES OF FACTORS AFFECTING BUYING BEHAVIOUR (BUYING DECISIONS)

1. Influence of Culture on Buying Decisions

Factor		Highly Influenced	Influenced	Partially Influenced	Not Influenced
Culture	Frequency	64	220	108	08
	Percentage (%)	16	55	27	02

Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) 'D' Value 0.23 at an Alfa of 5%

2. Influence of Society on Buying Decisions

Factor		Highly Influenced	Influenced	Partially Influenced	Not Influenced
Society	Frequency	100	195	92	13
	Percentage (%)	25	48.75	23	03.25

Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) 'D' Value 0.24 at an Alfa of 5%

3. Influence of Family on Buying Decisions

Factor		Highly Influenced	Influenced	Partially Influenced	Not Influenced
Family	Frequency	260	120	16	04
	Percentage (%)	65	30	04	01

Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) 'D' Value 0.45 at an Alfa of 5%

4. Influence of Status in Society on Buying Decisions

Factor		Highly Influenced	Influenced	Partially Influenced	Not Influenced
Status in Society	Frequency	64	223	82	31
	Percentage (%)	16	55.75	20.50	07.75

Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) 'D' Value 0.22 at an Alfa of 5%

5. Influence of Role in Family on Buying Decisions

Factor		Highly Influenced	Influenced	Partially Influenced	Not Influenced
Role in Family	Frequency	57	132	179	32
	Percentage (%)	14.25	33	44.75	8

Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) 'D' Value 0.17 at an Alfa of 5%

6. Influence of Occupation on Buying Decisions

Factor		Highly Influenced	Influenced	Partially Influenced	Not Influenced
Occupation	Frequency	21	225	70	84
	Percentage (%)	05.25	56.25	17.50	21

Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) 'D' Value 0.11 at an Alfa of 5%

7. Influence of Education on Buying Decisions

Factor		Highly Influenced	Influenced	Partially Influenced	Not Influenced
Education	Frequency	64	215	104	17
	Percentage (%)	16	53.75	26	04.25

Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) 'D' Value 0.21 at an Alfa of 5%

8. Influence of Experience on Buying Decisions

Factor		Highly Influenced	Influenced	Partially Influenced	Not Influenced
Experience	Frequency	56	213	108	23
	Percentage (%)				

Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) 'D' Value 0.19 at an Alfa of 5%

9. Influence of Economic Status on Buying Decisions

Factor		Highly Influenced	Influenced	Partially Influenced	Not Influenced
Economic Status	Frequency	52	200	80	68
	Percentage (%)	13	50	20	17

Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) 'D' Value 0.13 at an Alfa of 5%

10. Influence of Life Style on Buying Decisions

Factor		Highly Influenced	Influenced	Partially Influenced	Not Influenced
Life Style	Frequency	120	128	112	40
	Percentage (%)	30	32	28	10

Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) 'D' Value 0.15 at an Alfa of 5%

11. Influence of Personality on Buying Decisions

Factor		Highly Influenced	Influenced	Partially Influenced	Not Influenced
Personality	Frequency	68	205	78	49
	Percentage (%)	17	51.25	19.50	12.25

Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) 'D' Value 0.18 at an Alfa of 5%

12. Influence of Age & Life Cycle Stage on Buying Decisions

Factor		Highly Influenced	Influenced	Partially Influenced	Not Influenced
Age & Life Cycle Stage	Frequency	188	94	107	11
	Percentage (%)				

Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) 'D' Value 0.23 at an Alfa of 5%

13. Influence of Attitude on Buying Decisions

Factor		Highly Influenced	Influenced	Partially Influenced	Not Influenced
Attitude	Frequency	28	217	83	72
	Percentage (%)	7	54.25	20.75	18

Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) 'D' Value 0.11 at an Alfa of 5%

14. Influence of Motivation on Buying Decisions

Factor		Highly Influenced	Influenced	Partially Influenced	Not Influenced
Motivation	Frequency	112	249	32	07
	Percentage (%)	28	62.25	8	1.75

Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) 'D' Value 0.40 at an Alfa of 5%

15. Influence of Perception on Buying Decisions

Factor		Highly Influenced	Influenced	Partially Influenced	Not Influenced
Perception	Frequency	45	221	122	12
	Percentage (%)	11.25	55.25	30.50	3

Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) 'D' Value 0.22 at an Alfa of 5%

16. Influence of Beliefs on Buying Decisions

Factor		Highly Influenced	Influenced	Partially Influenced	Not Influenced
Beliefs	Frequency	10	83	242	65
	Percentage (%)	2.50	20.75	60.50	16.25

Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) 'D' Value 0.09 at an Alfa of 5%

17. Influence of Store Image on Buying Decisions

Factor		Highly Influenced	Influenced	Partially Influenced	Not Influenced
Store Image	Frequency	96	126	129	49
	Percentage (%)	24	31.50	32.25	12.25

Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) 'D' Value 0.128 at an Alfa of 5%

18. Influence of Retailers' Image

Factor		Highly Influenced	Influenced	Partially Influenced	Not Influenced
Store Image	Frequency	121	131	97	51
	Percentage (%)	30.25	32.75	24.25	12.75

Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) 'D' Value 0.130 at an Alfa of 5%

SECTION V

ANALYSIS OF SATISFACTION LEVEL OF CUSTOMERS OF ORGANIZED RETAILERS

1. Satisfaction Level with Variety of Products Offered by Retailers

Factor		Highly Satisfied	Satisfied	Neither Satisfied Nor Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Highly Dissatisfied
Variety of Products	Frequency	156	126	50	42	26
	Percentage (%)	39	31.50	12.50	10.50	6.50

Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) 'D' Value 0.305 at an Alfa of 5%

2. Satisfaction Level with Different Brands in each Category offered by Retailers

Factor		Highly Satisfied	Satisfied	Neither Satisfied Nor Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Highly Dissatisfied
Different Brands in each Category	Frequency	109	134	72	64	21
	Percentage (%)	27.25	33.50	18	16	5.25

Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) 'D' Value 0.208 at an Alfa of 5%

3. Satisfaction level with Arrangement for Display of Goods in Store

Factor		Highly Satisfied	Satisfied	Neither Satisfied Nor Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Highly Dissatisfied
Arrangement for Display of Goods	Frequency	98	130	76	68	28
	Percentage (%)	24.50	32.50	19	17	7

Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) 'D' Value 0.170 at an Alfa of 5%

4. Satisfaction with Availability of New Launched Product by Retailers

Factor		Highly Satisfied	Satisfied	Neither Satisfied Nor Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Highly Dissatisfied
Availability of New Launched Product	Frequency	102	136	70	62	30
	Percentage (%)	25.50	34	17.50	15.50	7.50

Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) 'D' Value 0.195 at an Alfa of 5%

5. Satisfaction with Price Charged from Customers for Products & Services

Factor		Highly Satisfied	Satisfied	Neither Satisfied Nor Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Highly Dissatisfied
Price Charged from Customers	Frequency	54	112	92	90	52
	Percentage (%)	13.50	28	23	22.50	13

Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) 'D' Value 0.070 at an Alfa of 5%

6. Satisfaction with Discounts & Schemes offered by Retailers

Factor		Highly Satisfied	Satisfied	Neither Satisfied Nor Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Highly Dissatisfied
Discounts & Schemes	Frequency	109	132	71	67	21
	Percentage (%)					

Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) 'D' Value 0.203 at an Alfa of 5%

7. Satisfaction with Information Provided regarding Discounts & Schemes by Retailers

Factor		Highly Satisfied	Satisfied	Neither Satisfied Nor Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Highly Dissatisfied
Information regarding Discounts & Schemes	Frequency	54	122	92	88	44
	Percentage (%)	13.50	30.50	23	22	11

Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) 'D' Value 0.090 at an Alfa of 5%

8. Satisfaction with Billing Facilities

Factor		Highly Satisfied	Satisfied	Neither Satisfied Nor Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Highly Dissatisfied
Billing Facilities	Frequency	106	122	78	64	30
	Percentage (%)	26.50	30.50	19.50	16	7.50

Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) 'D' Value 0.170 at an Alfa of 5%

9. Satisfaction with Advertising Methods Adopted

Factor		Highly Satisfied	Satisfied	Neither Satisfied Nor Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Highly Dissatisfied
Advertising Methods	Frequency	100	130	80	58	32
	Percentage (%)	25	32.50	20	14.50	8

Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) 'D' Value 0.170 at an Alfa of 5%

10. Satisfaction with Nature & Behaviour of Employees of Retail Stores

Factor		Highly Satisfied	Satisfied	Neither Satisfied Nor Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Highly Dissatisfied
Nature & Behaviour of Employees	Frequency	96	128	78	62	36
	Percentage (%)	24	32	19.50	15.50	9

Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) 'D' Value 0.160 at an Alfa of 5%

11. Satisfaction with After Sale Services on Durable Goods

Factor		Highly Satisfied	Satisfied	Neither Satisfied Nor Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Highly Dissatisfied
After Sale Services on Durable Goods	Frequency	82	124	92	56	46
	Percentage (%)	20.50	31	23	14	11.50

Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) 'D' Value 0.145 at an Alfa of 5%

12. Satisfaction with Safety provided to your Personal Goods

Factor		Highly Satisfied	Satisfied	Neither Satisfied Nor Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Highly Dissatisfied
Safety provided to your Personal Goods	Frequency	92	116	82	76	34
	Percentage (%)	23	29	20.50	19	8.50

Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) 'D' Value 0.125 at an Alfa of 5%

13. Satisfaction with Parking & Lift Facilities

Factor		Highly Satisfied	Satisfied	Neither Satisfied Nor Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Highly Dissatisfied
Parking & Lift Facilities	Frequency	112	126	80	49	33
	Percentage (%)	28	31.50	20	12.50	8.25

Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) 'D' Value 0.195 at an Alfa of 5%

14. Satisfaction with Location of Outlets

Factor		Highly Satisfied	Satisfied	Neither Satisfied Nor Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Highly Dissatisfied
Location of Outlets	Frequency	136	112	80	40	32
	Percentage (%)	34	28	20	10	8

Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) 'D' Value 0.220 at an Alfa of 5%

15. Satisfaction with Timings of Outlet

Factor		Highly Satisfied	Satisfied	Neither Satisfied Nor Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Highly Dissatisfied
Timings of Outlet	Frequency	102	133	77	56	32
	Percentage (%)	25.50	33.25	19.25	14	8

Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) 'D' Value 0.118 at an Alfa of 5%

16. Satisfaction with Store Environment

Factor		Highly Satisfied	Satisfied	Neither Satisfied Nor Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Highly Dissatisfied
Store Environment	Frequency	52	134	92	76	46
	Percentage (%)	13	33.50	23	19	11.50

Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) 'D' Value 0.095 at an Alfa of 5%

17. Satisfaction with Customer Services

Factor		Highly Satisfied	Satisfied	Neither Satisfied Nor Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Highly Dissatisfied
Customer Services	Frequency	92	103	104	69	32
	Percentage (%)					

Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) 'D' Value 0.148 at an Alfa of 5%

18. Satisfaction with Attention Paid to Customer Problems

Factor		Highly Satisfied	Satisfied	Neither Satisfied Nor Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Highly Dissatisfied
Attention Paid to Customer Problems	Frequency	52	99	132	78	39
	Percentage (%)	13	24.75	33	19.50	9.75

Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) 'D' Value 0.108 at an Alfa of 5%

19. Satisfaction with Refreshment Facilities

Factor		Highly Satisfied	Satisfied	Neither Satisfied Nor Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Highly Dissatisfied
Refreshment Facilities	Frequency	49	96	125	87	43
	Percentage (%)	12.25	24	31.25	21.75	10.75

Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) 'D' Value 0.075 at an Alfa of 5%

20. Satisfaction with Entrainment Facilities

Factor		Highly Satisfied	Satisfied	Neither Satisfied Nor Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Highly Dissatisfied
Entrainment Facilities	Frequency	62	84	132	78	44
	Percentage (%)	15.50	21	33	19.50	11

Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) 'D' Value 0.095 at an Alfa of 5%

DISCUSSIONS

Results delineate majority of customers (59.50%) were male and other majority (40.50%) were female, in which most of customers (76%) were married.

This indicates that women are also taking interest in purchasing. Majority of respondents (39.75%) belonged to age group of 16-30 years and most of customers (72%) were graduate likely and above. This indicates that young and well educated people like to visit organized retail outlets.

Majority of customers (71.75%) were working, in which most of customers (43.75%) were salaried. Majority of women visiting retails outlet (65%) were working. Majority of customers' (86.75%) house hold incomes were one Lakh likely and above per annum. The above facts point out that working people especially salaried and people having good house hold income prefer to visit retail outlets.

Majority of customers (78.25%) belonged to nuclear family, in which most of customers (67.75%) belonged to the family of 2-5 members. Majority of customers (74%) resided in urban area. This explains that mostly customers of organized retailers belong to nuclear family and urban areas.

Results also delineate majority of customers (59.75%) made their purchase decisions by self and most of the customers (71.50%) did purchasing on demand of family.

Majority of respondents (72%) collected the information while making purchase decisions, in which most of the customers (54.50%) collected the information from advertising, other majority (50.25%) from family members, and other majority (48%) from neighbors/friends/relatives. This states that there is a huge change in buying behavior of people in India due to increase in literacy level. Now women also make

purchase decisions for family and people collect the information regarding products and services while making purchase decisions.

Majority of customers (52%) visited organized retailers for more than two years. Most of customers (58.50%) visited retail outlet three times likely and more per month. Majority of customers (62%) spend Rs. 2000/- likely and more per month. This carry out that people spend enough to shop from these retail outlets due to increase in income level of people.

Majority of customers (70.25%) preferred Saturday-Sunday and other majority (17.25%) preferred Wednesday (Due to sales promotional activities of Big Bazaar) to visit retail outlets, in which most of the customers (71.25%) preferred to visit in the evening time. This finalizes that customers prefer to visit on weekend days and evening time.

Majority of customers' purchase decisions (72.25%) influenced by family members, other majority (58.75%) by neighbors/friends/relatives. This discloses that in India, today also, majority of decisions influenced by family and society.

Most of customers (54.50%) purchased all types of products like food and grocery, apparel, consumer durables and others. This indicates that customers are interested to buy all types of products under one roof.

Majority of customers (93.25%) visited these retail outlets due to variety of products, other majority (79.50%) due to proximity to home/office, other majority (77.50%) due to discounts and schemes, other majority (51.75%) due to billing through plastic money and other majority (48.50%) due to good customer services. Most of the customers (61%) visited more than one retailer due to several reasons. This argues on loyalty status of customers in organized retail industry, results depict that there is less loyalty among Indian customers.

Study depicts most of customers (66%) were brand and quality conscious and other majority (34%) were interested in price, discounts, schemes and quantity. This shows that there is a huge change in the preference of Indian consumer. Now customer's preference is shifting towards quality and brand from price, discounts, schemes and others.

To analyze the influences of factors affecting buying behavior, some relevant factors were asked to rate on ordinal (influence) scale with content highly influenced, influenced, partially influenced and not influenced. To find out the degree of influence between a set of value observed and values specified by the null hypothesis, Kolmogorov-Smirnov One Sample test has been applied. Result delineates calculated Kolmogorov-Smirnov D Value for each factor. The critical value of D at an alpha of 0.05 is 0.068. As the calculated D exceeds the critical value of 0.068, the null hypothesis that there is no significant influence of factors on buying decisions is rejected with all the factors.

To analyze the satisfaction level of customers, some relevant services were asked to rate on Likert five point scales ranging from highly dissatisfy to highly satisfy with the middle of the scale identifies by the response alternative neither satisfy not dissatisfy. To find out the degree of satisfaction between a set of value observed and values specified by the null hypothesis, Kolmogorov-Smirnov one sample test has been applied. Result delineates calculated Kolmogorov-Smirnov D Value for each service. The critical value of D at an alpha of 0.05 is 0.068. As the calculated D exceeds the critical value of 0.068, the null hypothesis that there is no significant satisfaction among customers with regards to various services rendered by organized retailers in Pune is rejected in case of all the services.

CHAPTER-5

CONCLUSIONS

The aim of the research was to analyze, changes in buying behavior of customers of organized retailers and levels of customer satisfaction with regards to various products and services offered organized retailers in Pune city. From the research, we can conclude the following-

For a normal person who see a retail store thinks that retail stores are building having products only but actually these retailers are providing and playing a very important role in economic development of the country which is not feasible for a normal person.

Study delineates that there is a huge change in buying behavior of Indian consumers in terms of their purchase decisions making, information collection decisions, preference while making purchase decisions, money spending, and loyalty due to increase in literacy rate, household income, working women population, nuclear families, changes in life style, and young demographics of Indian consumers.

Results point out that there is a significant influence of factors on buying decisions of customers viz... culture, society, family, status in society, role in family, occupation, education, experience, economic status, life style, personality, age and life cycle stage, attitude, perception, beliefs, motivation, store image and retailers' image.

Results indicate that there is a significant satisfaction among customers with regards to various services rendered by organized retailers in Pune city viz... variety of products, different brands in each category, arrangement for display of goods (visual merchandising), availability of new launched products, price charged from customers, discounts and schemes, information provided regarding discounts and schemes, billing

facilities, advertising methods adopted, nature and behavior of employees, after sale services on durable goods, attention paid to their problems, customer services, refreshment facilities, entertainment facilities, safety provided to personal goods of customers, parking and lift facilities, location and timings of outlets, and ambience.

Retailers know that customer satisfaction is prime necessity to reinforce customer's trust, commitment, repurchase intention, positive word of mouth, retention, and financial performance of any organization.

At the time of survey customers suggested some additional services like loyalty schemes, home delivery services, deposit schemes with guaranteed rebate, products on demand, gift on bulk purchase, membership facility, internet billing facility, and insurance cover etc.

Today, retailing is much more than mere merchandising. As the Indian consumers evolve, they expect much more each time they step into a store. While insisting on value for money and cost effectiveness, today consumers want a better shopping experience, recreation, friendly interactions and a wide choice of products and services. Customers also want to eat, shop, and get entertained under same roof. Consumer expectations are very high from the organized retail stores. Such expectations may not be fulfilled by conventional stores so organized retailers have to fulfill all these expectations in order to flourish, thrive, and germinate by leaps & bounds in the Indian market.

Firstly, retail marketing has more human element in it, and hence personal skills, attitudes and motivation play a greater role, than in product marketing. Secondly, retail marketing needs a more fortified, cohesive and interactive organization and hence the needed organizational skills for retail marketing are different. Thirdly, the personal touch and quality are more important in retail marketing sector. Fourthly, retail marketing being specific to customer and customer to be treated as a king, his satisfaction is paramount in retailing sector of Pune city.

In this new competitive environment and globalize trade practices, the marketing in organized retail assumed greater significance. Today's organized retail market requires new strategies to survive and continue to operate. They have to adopt new marketing strategies and practices which enable to capture the minimum opportunities with the lowest risks in order to enable them to survive and meet the tough competition from global players of domestic and foreign origin.

NEW CHALLENGES TO THE ORGANIZED RETAILERS

The challenges posed to the organized retail sector in the market place are many but some of them can be given as following:

- 1) Deregulation
- 2) Advanced information technology
- 3) Globalize markets and growing volumes of retail transactions
- 4) Volatility of the markets
- 5) Increased customer's demands and Sophistication of the markets and customers

Many of the existing could not cope with this new environment. Most of them sought to strengthen themselves by mergers and acquisitions, diversification or closer of some business lines which are uneconomical.

Others have met the challenges by better management talent, adoption of a new organization structure, strengthening of the information system and technology and drastic changes in their marketing strategies.

Adoption of all risk management strategies, soundly formulated business plans, acquiring new innovative talents, SWOT analysis, and correction of weakness and threats while making full utilization of their strengths and opportunities.

BASIC BRICKS FOR CUSTOMER SATISFACTION IN ORGANIZED RETAIL SECTOR

To enable a retailer to formulate its unique marketing strategy to meet challenges of the retail market scene, it has to be familiar with the various laws, environment constraints, its potential customers and their requirements, its competitors and their charges etc. Some of the key elements which are basis for formulating the strategies are as follow:

Customer Focus-

That customer is the king and his requirements are to be satisfied in full is the basic talent of any marketing strategy. This customer focus is to be incorporated in marketing, management and back office operations that have immediate access to customer. There is need for effective innovative scheme suitable to customer and retailers should provide timely delivery of services that the customer has asked for and meets with his requirements.

Capturing the Growth Opportunities-

In the competitive world, information is available to note what competitors offer. To gain upper hand, any smart business unit should identify the new business opportunities and realistically anticipate the demand or create a demand, which is easily and convincingly saleable to potential customers, after analyzing the risk-return scenario of the project realistically associated with each opportunity before deciding on the choice of pursuing it or not.

Successful Differentiation-

Success in a competitive world demands a retailer's ability to create a different product image in the mind of target customer groups. The product and services offered by the

retailer should be rated as different as superior to others in the line and should have been priced competitively. As in the case of product, differentiation of services rendered counts and its can be built in the mind of customer through assiduous efforts of communication, direct letters, display of their special features through presentations and effective mouth to mouth communications either from the company or its satisfied customers or their votaries.

Innovativeness and Management Ability-

Ultimately, the success of a retailer's marketing strategies depends on whether it is innovative and the extent of its innovativeness. For this the ability and expertise of the management is all that matters. They should be able to prove creative and innovative and ability to operate with new and unfamiliar customer and market place. Innovation drives organizations to grow, prosper and transform in sync with the changes in the environment, both internal and external. Retailing is no exception to this. In fact, this sector has witnessed radical transformation of late, based on many innovations in products, processes, services, systems, business models, technology, governance and regulation. A liberalized and globalize retailing infrastructure has provided an additional impetus to this gigantic effort.

The pervasive influence of information technology has revolutionaries retailing. Transaction costs have crumbled and handling of astronomical number of transactions in no time has become a reality. Internationally, the number brick and mortar structure has been rapidly yielding ground to click and order electronic retailing with a plethora of new products. Retailing has become boundary less and virtual with a 24 * 7 model. Retailers who strongly rely on the merits of relationship retailing' as a time tested way of targeting and serving clients, have readily embraced Customer Relationship Management (CRM), with sharp focus on customer centricity, facilitated by the availability of superior technology. CRM has, therefore, become the new mantra in customer service management, which is both relationship based and information intensive.

Risk management is no longer a mere regulatory issue. Basel-2 has accorded a primacy of place to this fascinating exercise by repositioning it as the core of retailing.

Quality and Professionalism-

Much more than in the product markets, service markets are prone to depend on subjective factors of image, reputation, quality of service and professionalism in management. The customers are enlightened and quality conscious and are highly demanding in the present day competitive environment. Service quality, delivery system and process and timeliness and conformity with specifications are the pre-requisites for a successful marketing strategy. Skills, training and education of all the human factors at various levels in the retails is a vital necessity for any marketing strategy to succeed. In the retailing sector, human factor, skills and quality are all vital to success, for which the adopted technology and skills count vary much.

Technology in Retailing-

Nobel Laureate Robert Solow had once remarked that computers are seen everywhere excepting in productivity statistics. More recent developments have shown how far this state of affairs has changed. Innovation in technology and worldwide revolution in information and communication technology (ICT) have emerged as dynamic sources of productivity growth. The relationship between IT and retailing is fundamentally symbiotic. In the retailing sector, IT can reduce costs, increase volumes, and facilitate customized products.

Information technology has immense untapped potential in retailing. Strengthening of information technology in retail could improve the effectiveness of asset-liability management in retailing. Building up of a related data-base on a real time basis would enhance the forecasting of liquidity greatly even at the store level. This could contribute to enhancing the risk management capabilities of retailers.

Knowledge Management-

According to Peter Drucker and Daniel Bell, the management Gurus knowledge is the only meaningful economic resource. Knowledge management can be defined as a systematic and integrative process of coordinating organization-wide activities of acquiring, creating, storing, sharing, diffusing, developing and deploying knowledge by individual and groups in the pursuit of major retailer's goals. It also involves the creation of an interacting learning environment where retailers members transfer and share what they know; and apply knowledge to solve problems, innovate and create new knowledge.

Knowledge management is as much about people and culture as it is about technology. Knowledge management thrives only when the human communication network operates freely across the shortest path between the knowledge providers and knowledge seekers. There must be a culture that promotes and rewards the pooling together of knowledge resources. Thus retailers must build a culture that motivates people to create, share and use knowledge.

After the preoccupation with system and procedures to collect data and translate it into information, its time for firms to focus on the next plane- knowledge. Knowledge management is not a buzzword. Every knowledge management solution, if currently implemented, has definite measurable business benefits.

Future business success increasingly depends on the retention and the creative use of the knowledge ideas and experiences of a retailer and its employees. And in knowledge economy corporations need for workers will be more than the workers need for employer.

Concept Selling-

Some concepts like retailing and home retailing or internet trading or e-mail retailing are examples of concept building and selling of services. I.T. and T.V. can be used as a media for this purpose.

The likely determinants of service quality may be briefly set out as follows:

- 1) Reliability which includes timely performance and dependability of the service.
- 2) Responsiveness of the management to the needs of customers, to effect any necessary changes or incorporate new ideas etc.
- 3) Competence and skills of the personnel in the vendor form counts for dependability of quality.
- 4) Courtesy and effective communication with the client by the firm and consistency in their approach counts for infusing confidence in the customer.
- 5) Understanding the requirements of the customer and knowing them fully well also helps the retailers the quality requirements and the demands to satisfy the customer completely.
- 6) Credibility involving trustworthiness, honesty and integrity of the retailers providing services will add to its name and reputation to provide the quality service required.
- 7) Security and freedom from any risk or uncertainty for the customer from the retailers in respect of timeliness and quality of service is equally important.
- 8) Most important of all, management skills, their professionalism in approach their easy access to the clients, and willingness to help and amend with positive attitudes will infuse confidence in the customers on the competency of management to deliver the quality service in time.

Strengthening the Link between Marketing Strategy and Financial Performance-

From the perspective that integrates marketing and retailing practice and theory, the relevance of interactions between the issues of 'what' (marketing strategy) and 'why' (financial performance). The key finding is that the marketing strategy–financial performance link faces serious difficulties, but they do not inevitably prevent the promotion and greater acceptance of the basic idea. The strongest barriers include negative attitudes of marketers to the language of financial indicators, different paradigms of people from marketing and retailing, insufficient presence of the key

concepts in the basic literature and unrealistic requirements of academic models. On the other side, the demand that becomes more powerful and sophisticated, and intensifying competition are the major drivers of positive changes in practice and theory. Greater respect for risk indicators, improved short-term/long-term balance, stronger integration of marketing strategy elements, as well as more realistic general frameworks, constitute the group of encouraging trends.

Customer Relationship Management-

Today, retailers are facing an aggressive competition and they have to make efforts to survive in a competitive and uncertain market place. Retailers have realized that managing customer relationships is a very important factor for their success in whole country. Customer relationship management (CRM) is a strategy that can help them to build long-lasting relationships with their customers and increase their profits through the right management system and the application of customer-focused strategies. CRM in the retailing sector is of strategic importance. CRM is a sound business strategy to identify the retailer's most profitable customers and prospects. While the debate rages on concerning the importance of customer lifetime value and relationship marketing, in my opinion and experience, relationship exchanges between buyers and sellers can help establish differentiation and create barriers to switching. Furthermore, establishing strong internal and external stakeholder relationships based on trust, commitment and value are essential to sustainable competitive advantages. The majority of the relationship marketing, value creation and management literature discussing RM future trends seem to center on importance of developing relationships and lifetime customer value. They highlight the value of stakeholders in terms of customers, staff, suppliers, influencers and partners – constituting a company's most precious assets. Globalization has created an environment of intense competition, price wars human capital issues, product and services becoming commodities and technology invading every aspect of business. After all is said and done, the core to a company's real value and worth are its relationships.

Relationships are fundamental to every company's long term success. Companies that acknowledge and comprehend the value of relationships and how to leverage them to enhance value will surface as the market leaders and maintain a competitive market advantage. Therefore, the development of effective RM platforms that demonstrate trust and commitment is crucial to profitable relational customers, maximizing overall customer lifetime value and bottom line results.

Products and Services-

The complexion of the retailing sector has changed dramatically in terms of products and services in a market where the customer has more options than ever before and retailers are compelled to review constantly their package of products and services. Retailers in Pune City, traditionally, offered mass products. With the reforms came a massive expansion of products and services driven by technological advances that had a dramatic impact on the delivery systems and the ability to service a greater number of products.

Profitability, the new mantra in retailing, forced retailers to transform into financial supermarkets. The focus has shifted to class retailing with value-added and customized products for diverse customers.

Retailers with differentiated products targeted at customer groups, rather than treating products as homogenous commodities will be the winners. Product promotion and marketing product innovation in retailing call for newer strategies. For historical reasons, product promotion has so far remained low on retailers' agenda. Product marketing and market intelligence are still in their infancy.

Marketing has become crucial for a retailer's success - in terms of profitability, innovative product development, optimum use of infrastructure, expanding market, and so on.

Product Branding-

In recent years, increasing attention has been paid to positioning and, more specifically, positioning of product/service brands. This is so because of the unique characteristics of products/services. Although some marketers argue that there are no marked differences between positioning in services and that of physical goods, the vast majority of markets believe that it is difficult to embark on positioning strategies in services. Branding is becoming more important in market today, with global brands creating severe competition for local brands, and the pace of change in the information age meaning product life cycles are shortening dramatically, especially in product classes such as computers and peripherals, information services, fashion and health care.

Customers today are looking for convenience - where and how to offer the product no longer matters. This is why branding is gaining in importance, especially with escalating competition. Traditionally, retailing brands have been particularly difficult to build. In fact, with fierce competition, there is little or no sustainable product innovation/differentiation -- either in product features or the price. Clearly, there is room for powerful and winning brands.

Pricing of Products-

Stiff competition is making it difficult for retailers to price their products and services on cost-plus basis as hitherto. In the current competitive scene and the levels of product sophistication, the traditional cost-benefit approach to product pricing needs to be supplemented with more scientific and product specific pricing strategies.

Activity-based pricing with the aid of scientific methods based on customer preferences is essential. Most customers do not mind paying a little extra if they get the service they want. In pricing products, the importance of strengthening the bottom-line has to be borne in mind. With shrinking spreads, retailers will have to do a tight-rope walking to meet the depositors' demand for increasing interest, and the borrowers' clamour for lower

the coupon. In such a situation, only product innovation can help. It would also help retailers cut costs and achieve economies of scale and improve their bottom-line by increased volumes. They will be able to reduce and diversify risks in their asset portfolios and contain NPA levels. Innovative products, such as asset securitization, are bound to open new vistas in sustaining optimal capital adequacy and asset liability management of retailers.

Re-engineering of business through sophisticated technology-based products will not only lead to business creation, but also cut operational expenses and enhance the efficiency of operations.

Retailers that have the strength and the competence to convert these challenges in to opportunities will be the winners. "Simply catching up to where others have been is necessary to stay in the game, but the winners will be those who have the ability to invent fundamentally new games."

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Retailers are adopting the traditional promotional tools for the growth of products/services. For the higher growth of products/services retailers should use integrated marketing communication tools.
2. Although all the retailers are considering customer relationship as the prime goal to attract the customers and they are also trying to maintain good customer relationship but in the today marketing scenario, “customer is the king” so that’s why retailers should maintain a customer relationship management department and they should analyze and apply customer relationship at household level, at account level and at individual level.
3. As we know customer is the prime element for any business. Mostly the key customers of retailers are in 16-45 years age group. The recommendation is that retailers should segment the target market on demographic base factor (age) to attract all the customers of different age group.
4. All the customers’ categories are having equal importance for any retailer still that mostly retailers concentrate only on the retail clientele. So, retailers should consider all the category of clientele (retail as well as corporate) with equal importance to attract more and more target customers.
5. Marketing mix is the key element or vital role player element to attract the customer to the product. According to the research of selected retailers for the study, retailers are considering people mix and product mix as a greater importance (factor) element. For the betterment, retailers should implement whole service marketing mix tools.
6. Nothing is better than to know about your customer. According to the research of retailers, in general mostly retailers obtain the information regarding their customers either from existing customers or personal relation. So, to receive the information

- regarding the customer in the more appropriate way company should use the various marketing research tools.
7. Store level planning is the important decision to increase the efficiency of the particular store for a retailer. So, retailers should use the different and diversified tools available for store-level planning to increase the efficiency and effectiveness.
 8. Risk management is necessary factor to win the faith of a customer and to survive in a market for a long time. That's why retailers should follow strictly risk management practices for the betterment and to run successfully for a long time with winning the customer faith.
 9. Pricing strategy is a headache for the retailers. What should be the appropriate pricing strategy is the crucial task in front of marketing person. Is it should be according to the customer or competitor or market. Retailers should make and imply the different – different pricing strategy in every different region, according to the customer, market and competitors.
 10. Motivation factors are playing very vital role to attract the customers to the store. That's why retailers should also includes the motivation factors in their priority list of services provided to the customer i.e. full support to the customer in selecting products/services, rewards for good customer, efficient problem solving approach, full of helping nature concern and patience full store staff, time to time information regarding discounts & schemes, problem resolution via phone services, timely response to their queries, financial advice, accuracy and clarity of billing, convenient store timings, good appearance of office and parking facility etc.
 11. To increase the customer base in target market retailers should provide some essential services like loyalty schemes, home delivery services, deposit schemes with guaranteed rebate, products on demand, gift on bulk purchase, membership facility, internet billing facility, and insurance cover etc.

12. According to the survey, customers were not satisfied with the price charged for the product & services. That's why retailers should do something in order to improve the customer satisfaction.
13. According to the consumer study, customers were not happy with the ambience, entertainment facilities and refreshment facilities provided by retailers. Retailers should provide such type of facilities in order to grow by leaps and bounds in the Indian retail market.
14. As we heard that as a retailer you never get a second chance to make a first impression. Therefore, it is important to create a good store image. A good store image entices customers to make a purchase, spend more money and time, revisit, impulse purchase, also maintain customer interest and enhance frequency to visit store. Store image has also impact on store choice, store satisfaction, store loyalty, attitude towards store, and perceived risk. Furthermore, store image not only influence the customer perception, purchase intention, purchase making decisions, learning, life style, and benefits but also motivate customers to spread positive word of mouth. Therefore, store image is the critical success factor in the today's dynamic retailing environment.
15. Retailers' image is also an important consideration in purchase making decisions. Therefore, retailers should also enhance their image.
16. Indian customers also give the importance to different factors while taking purchase decisions like culture, society, family, status in society, role in family, occupation, education, experience, economic status, life style, personality, age and life cycle stage, attitude, motivation, perception, beliefs. Therefore, to be a good retailer, retailers should also take all these in to the consideration while setting the offering mix for the target market. By doing so, retailers can get the desired sales, revenue and profit from the target market.

CHAPTER 6

INDIVIDUAL QUESTIONNAIRE

1. Name of the Customer _____

2. Gender

- a) Male
- b) Female

3. Age (in years)

- a) Below 15
- b) 15-30
- c) 30-45
- d) 45-60
- e) Above 60

4. Contact Number _____

5. Marital Status

- a) Single
- b) Married

6. Education

- a) Illiterate
- b) Below 10th
- c) 10th -12th
- d) Graduate
- e) Postgraduate

7. Occupation

- a) Student
- b) Salaried
- c) Own Business
- d) House Wife
- e) Retired

8. Income (Yearly)

- a) Less than 1 Lakh
- b) 1 to 2 Lakhs
- c) 2 to 5 Lakhs
- d) More than 5 Lakhs

9. Nature of the Family

- a) Nuclear
- b) Joint

10. Total members in your family

- a) 2-3
- b) 4-5
- c) 6-7
- d) More than 7

11. Residing Area

- a) Urban
- b) Rural

12. How do you get influenced to buy a product?

- a) Self
- b) Family members
- c) Neighbors/Friends/Colleagues
- d) Advertising
- e) Others

13. Generally, who take the purchase making decision in your family?

- a) Self
- b) Spouse
- c) Children
- d) Parents
- e) Others

14. Do you collect the information, while purchase making decision?

- a) Yes
- b) No

-If yes, from where you collect the information regarding product?

- a) Advertising
- b) Family members
- c) Neighbors/Friends/Relatives
- d) Others

-If advertising, by which source?

- a) Television
- b) Newspapers
- c) Magazines
- d) Hoardings
- e) Pamphlets
- f) Others

15. Generally, who do the purchasing in your family?

- a) Self
- b) Spouse
- c) Children
- d) Parents
- e) Others

16. For how long, you have been visiting this retailer?

- a) First Time
- b) Last 6 months

- c) Last one year
- d) Last two year
- e) More than Two year

17. How frequently you visit this retail store in a month?

- a) 1 Time
- b) 2 Times
- c) 3 Times
- d) 4 Times
- e) More than 4 times

18. On which day of the weak, you prefer to visit this retail store?

- a) Monday-Tuesday
- b) Wednesday
- c) Thursday-Friday
- d) Saturday-Sunday
- e) Any Day

19. When you prefer to visit this retail store?

- a) Morning
- b) Afternoon
- c) Evening
- d) Any Time

20. How much you spend for purchasing from this retail store in a month?

- a) < Rs. 1000
- b) Rs. 1000-2000
- c) Rs. 2001-5000
- d) > Rs. 5000

21. What type of products, you purchase from this retail store?

- a) Food and Grocery
- b) Apparel
- c) Consumer Durables

- d) Others
- e) All

22. Why do you visit this retail store?

- a) Proximity to home/office
- b) Variety of products
- c) Reasonable prices
- d) Discount & special schemes
- e) Good customer services
- f) Good & spacious ambience
- g) Behavior of employees
- h) Billing through plastic money

23. Do you visit any other retail outlet apart from this?

- a) Yes
- b) No

24. If, Yes than what is the cause-

- a) Proximity to home/office
- b) Variety of products
- c) Reasonable prices
- d) Discount & special schemes
- e) Good customer services
- f) Good & spacious ambience
- g) Behavior of employees
- h) Billing through plastic money

25. While purchasing, you give the preference to-

(Put number 1,2,3,4 & 5 in order of preference)

- a) Brand
- b) Quality
- c) Price
- d) Discounts & Schemes
- e) Others

26. How do your buying decisions affected with these factors-

Sr. No.	Factors Influencing Buying Decisions	Influence Scale*			
		4	3	2	1
1.	Culture				
2.	Society				
3.	Family				
4.	Status in Society				
5.	Role in Family				
6.	Occupation				
7.	Education				
8.	Experience				
9.	Economic Status				
10.	Life Style				
11.	Personality				
12.	Age and Life Cycle Stage				
13.	Attitude				
14.	Motivation				
15.	Perception				
16.	Beliefs				
17.	Store Image				
18.	Retailers' Image				
*4- Highly Influenced, 3- Influenced, 2- Partially Influenced, 1- Not Influenced					

27. How do you satisfied with difference services rendered by your retailer-

Sr. No.	Factors	Satisfaction Scale*				
		5	4	3	2	1
1.	Variety of Products					
2.	Different Brands in each Category					
3.	Arrangement for Display of Goods					
4.	Availability of New Launched Product					
5.	Price charged from Customers					
6.	Discounts and schemes					
7.	Information Provided regarding Discounts & Schemes					
8.	Billing Facilities					
9.	Advertising Methods Adopted					
10.	Nature & Behavior of Employee					
11.	After Sale Services on Durable Goods					
12.	Safety provided to your Personal Goods					
13.	Parking & Lift Facilities					
14.	Location of Outlets					
15.	Timings of Outlet					
16.	Ambience					
17.	Customer Services					
18.	Refreshment Facilities					
19.	Entertainment Facilities					
20.	Attention paid to customer's problems					
<p>* 5- Highly Satisfied, 4- Satisfied, 3- Neither Satisfied Nor Dissatisfied, 2- Dissatisfied, 1- Highly Dissatisfied</p>						

28. According to you, what other facilities should be provided by retailer?

Sr. No.	Facilities	Tick
1	Loyalty Schemes	
2	Home delivery services	
3	Deposit schemes with guaranteed rebate	
4	Product on demand	
5	Gift on bulk purchase	
6	Membership facility	
7	Internet billing facility	
8	Insurance cover	
9	Medical facility	
10	Internet facility	
11	Any other, specify-	
12	Any other, specify-	
13	Any other, specify-	
14	Any other, specify-	

Suggestions (If Any)-

Thank You

Signature

CHAPTER 7

BIBLIOGRAPHY

A.K. Agarwal (2005) "Services Marketing- Stop, Observe, Go"- Indian Journal of Marketing, Vol- XXXV, No- 5, May.

Adrian J. Palmer (1995) "Relationship Marketing: Local Implementation of a Universal Concept"- International Business Review, Vol-4, No-3, Sept.

Anderson, E. W. and Sullival, V. W. (1993), "The antecedents and consequences of customer satisfaction to firms", Marketing Science, Vol. 12, No. 2, pp. 125-143.

Baptista and Estin (1995) "Can a company be both low-cost and service-oriented?"- The journal of services marketing, Vol- 9, No- 3.

Bei, Lien Ti and Chiao, Yu-ching (2001), "An integrated model for the effect of perceived product, perceived service quality and perceived price fairness on consumer satisfaction and loyalty", Journal of Consumer Satisfaction, Dissatisfaction and Complaining Behavior, Vol. 14.

Beri, G. C. (2008), Marketing Research, Tata McGraw Hill Publishing Company Ltd., New Delhi, India.

Broadbride, A. and Calderwood, E. (2002), "Rural grocery shoppers: do their attitudes reflect their actions?" Journal of Retailing and Distribution Management, Vol. 30, No. 8, pp. 394-406.

Brody, R. P. and Cunningham, S. M. (1960), "Personality variables consumer decision process", *Journal of Marketing Research*, Vol. 5, No. 1, pp. 50-57.

Brown, G. H. (1952), "Brand loyalty facts or fiction?", *Advertising Age*, Vol. 23, No. 1, pp. 53-55.

Chandan, Jean-Louis and Boris Bartikowski (2004) "An ordinal satisfaction scale allowing to classify respondents as "satisfied", "indifferent" or "dissatisfied"- *International Journal of Research in Marketing*, Vol- 19 (1).

Christian Homburg, Nicole Koschate, and Wayne D. Hayer (2005) "Do satisfied customers really pay more? A study of relationship between customer satisfaction and willingness to pay"- *Journal of Marketing*, Vol- 69, No- 2, April.

Churchill, G. A. Jr. and Surprenant, C. (1982), "An investigation into the determinants of the customer satisfaction", *Journal of Marketing Research*, Vol. XIX, November, pp. 491-504.

Das (2005) "Customerization: Getting to the Customer"- *ICFAI Journal of Marketing Management*, Vol- IV, No- 1, Feb.

Dhyani (2005) "Consumerism: Global V/s Indian Perspectives"- *Indian Journal of Marketing*, Vol- XXXV, No- 7, July.

Enis, B. M. and Paul, G. W. (1970), "Store loyalty as a basis for market segmentation", *Journal of Retailing*, Vol. 46, No. 3, pp. 42-56.

Farley, Ju (1964), "Why does 'Brand Loyalty' vary over products?", *Journal of Marketing Research*, Vol. 1, No. 4, pp. 9-14.

Fornell, C. (1992), "A national customer satisfaction barometer: the Swedish experience", *Journal of Marketing*, Vol. 56, No. 1, pp. 6-21.

Fraj, E. and Martinez, E. (2007), "Ecological consumer behavior: an empirical analysis", *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, Vol. 31, Issue 1, pp. 26-33.

George J. Avlonitis and Kostis A. Indounas (2005) "Pricing objectives and pricing methods in the services sector"- *Journal of Services Marketing*, Vol-19, No-1, 2.

Gerpott, T.; Rams, W. and Schindler, A. (2001), "Customer retention, loyalty and satisfaction in the German mobile cellular telecommunications market", *Telecommunication Policy*, Vol. 25, No. 4, pp. 249-269.

Goswami, P. and Mishra, M. (2007), "Would Indian consumers move from kirana store to organized retailers when shopping for groceries?", *Indian Journal of Marketing*.

Haemoun, Oh (1999), "Service quality, customer satisfaction and customer value: A holistic perspective", *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, Vol. 18, Issue 1, pp. 67-82.

Hamburg C. and Koschate N. (2004) "How do consumers react to price increases"- *International Journal of Research in Marketing*, Vol- 26 (4).

Harish, R. and Suchitra, K. (2010), "Sales promotions and their influences on consumer behavior", *Marketing Mastermind*, February 2010, pp. 21-24.

Hawkins, D. I.; Best, R. J.; Coney, K. A.; and Mookerjee, A. (2004), *Consumer Behavior- Building Marketing Strategy*, Tata McGraw Hill Publishing Company Ltd, India.

Hyllegard, K.; Eckman, M.; Descals, A. M.; and Borja, M. A. G. (2005), "Spanish consumer's perceptions of US apparel specialty retailer's product and services", *Journal of Consumer Behavior*, Vol. 4, Issue 5, pp. 345-362.

Jagdish N. Seth and Atul Parvatiyar (1995) "The Evolution of Relationship Marketing" – *International Business Review*, Vol-4, No-3, Sept.

James L. Walker (1995) "Service encounter satisfaction: conceptualized"- *Journal of services marketing*, Vol-9, No-1.

Johnson, M. D. and Fornell, C. (1991), "A framework for comparing customer satisfaction across individuals and product categories", *Journal of Economic Psychology*, Vol. 12, No. 2, pp. 267-286.

Kelly, S. W.; Douglas, Hoffman; and Mark, A. Davis, (1993), "A topology of retail failures and recoveries", *Journal of Retailing*, (69), pp. 429-452.

Kenneth E. Clow and John L. Beisel (1995) "Managing consumer expectations of low-margin, high-volume services"- *Journal of services marketing*, Vol- 9, No-1.

Knox, S. and Walker, D. (2003), "Empirical development in the measurement of involvement, brand loyalty and their relationship in grocery markets", *Journal of Strategic Marketing*, Vol. II, pp. 271-286.

Kothari, C. R. (2008), *Research Methodology*, New Age International (P) Ltd. Publications, New Delhi, India.

Kotler, P. & Armstrong, G. (2007), *Principal of Marketing*, Prentice-Hall Publication, New Delhi, India.

Laran, Juliano A and Espirioza, Francine S. (2005) “Satisfied Consumers? Analyzing satisfaction as an antecedent of loyalty”- International Journal of Research in Marketing, Vol- 8 (2), with reference to Vol- 22, No- 2, June.

Laurids Hedaa (1996) “Customer Acquisition in Sticky Business Markets” –International Business Review, Vol-5, No-5, Oct.

Liu, Yuping (2007), “The long term impact of loyalty programs on consumer purchase behaviour and loyalty”, Journal of Marketing, Vol. 71, Issue 4, pp. 19-35.

Lynthia Webster (1995) “Marketing culture and marketing effectiveness in service firms”- Journal of services marketing, Vol- 9, No- 2.

Maison, D.; Greenwald, Anthony A.; and Bruin, R. (2001), “The implicit association test as a measure of implicit consumer attitude”, Polish Psychological Bulletin, Vol. 32 (1).

Martin Fojt (1995) “Becoming a customer driven organization”- The journal of services marketing, Vol- 9, No- 3.

Martin Fojt (1995) “Calculating the return on quality”- The journal of services marketing, Vol- 9, No- 3.

Martin Fojt (1995) “Enhancing quality in service industries”- The journal of services marketing, Vol- 9, No- 3.

Mayer, M. (1989), “1949-1989: Retail Reflections”, Journal of Retailing, 65 (fall), pp. 396-401.

McGoldrick, P. J. and Andre, E. (1997), “Consumer misbehavior: promiscuity or loyalty in grocery shopping”, Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services, Vol. 4, No. 2, pp. 73-81.

Michael Lewis (2004) "The influence of loyalty programs and short-term promotions on customer retention"- *Journal of Marketing Research*, Vol- XLI, No- 3, August.

Miranda, M. J. and Konyal, Havrila I. (2005), "Shopper's satisfaction level are not the key to store loyalty", *Marketing Intelligence and Planning*, Vol. 23, No. 2, pp. 220-232.

Narayandas, N. (1996), "The link between customer satisfaction and customer loyalty: an empirical investigation", Working paper No. 97-017, Harvard Business School, Boston, M.A.

Nimit Choudhary and Monika Prahash (2005) "Service Quality: Revisting the two factors theory"- *Journal of Services Research*, Vol-5, No-1, April to Sept.

Oliver, L. R. (1980), "A cognitive model of the antecedents and consequences of satisfaction decisions", *Journal of Marketing Research*, Vol. 17, No. 4, pp. 460-469.

Oliver, L. Richard (1981), "Measurement and evaluation of satisfaction process in retail selling", *Journal of Retailing*, Vol. (57) 3, pp. 25-48.

Pan, Yue and Zinkhan, G. M. (2006), "Determination of retail patronage: meta analytical perspective", *Journal of Retailing*, (82), pp. 229-243.

Parasuraman, A.; Zeitham I. V.A.; and Berry, L. L. (1994), "Reassessment of expectations as a comparison standard in measuring services quality: implication for future research", *Journal of Marketing Research*, Vol. 58, pp. 111-124.

Parmar, Jay Singh and Gupta, Yasvant (2007), "Consumer behavior towards cosmetics: an empirical analysis", *Journal of IPM*, Meerut, India, pp. 44.

Pathak, S. V. and Tripathi, A. P. (2009), "Customer shopping behavior among modern retail formats: a study of Delhi and NCR", *Indian Journal of Marketing*, pp. 3-12.

Popai/Du Pont (1977), "Consumer buying habits study- supermarkets", (Point of purchase institute of the USA), New York.

Pradhan, S. (2009), *Retailing Management- Text & Cases*, Tata McGraw Hill Publishing Company Ltd., New Delhi, India.

Rajkumar Venkateran and V. Kumar (2004) "A customer lifetime value framework for customer selection and resource allocation strategy"- *Journal of Marketing*, Vol- 68, No- 4, Oct.

Ravi Dhar and Stephen M. Nowlis (2004) "To buy or not to buy: Response mode effects on consumer choice"- *Journal of Marketing Research*, Vol- XLI, No- 4, Nov.

Reichheld, F. F. and Sasser, W. E. (1990), "Zero defections: quality comes to services", *Harvard Business Review*, Vol. 68, Sept-Oct, pp. 301-307.

Richard A. Spreng, Gilbert D. Harrell and Robert D. Mackoy (1995) "Service recovery: impact on satisfaction and intentions"- *Journal of services marketing*, Vol- 9, No-1.

Robert A. W. Kole and BAS Hillebrand (2003) "What makes product development market oriented? Towards a conceptual framework." –*International journal of Innovation Management* Vol-7, No-2, June.

Robert Lensink and Niels Hermes (2004) "The short-term effects of foreign bank entry or domestic bank behavior: Does economic development matter?"- *Journal of Banking and Finance*, Vol- 28, Issue- 3, March.

Rodriguez, Paola R.; Lupin B.; and Lauragarrido, Gentile H. (2002), "Consumer behavior and super markets in Argentina", *Development Policy Review*, Vol. 20, pp. 429-439.

Ronald T. Rust, Katherine N. Lemon, and Valarie A. Zeithaml (2004) "Return on Marketing: Using Customer equity to focus on marketing strategy"- *Journal of Marketing*, Vol- 68, No- 1, Jan.

Sancheti, D. C. and Kapoor, V. K. (2000), *Statistics- Theory, Methods, & Applications*, Sultan Chand & Sons Education Publication, New Delhi, India.

Sanes (1995) "No news is bad news"- *The journal of services marketing*, Vol- 9, No- 3.

Sekhar, S. and Sahoo, S. K. (2009), "Organized retailing in India: issues and challenges", *Indian Journal of Marketing*, Vol. XXXIX (11), pp. 10-14.

Sevngaug Wern, Sharan E. Beatty and Michael A. Jones (2004) "The impact of service failure severity on service recovery evaluations and post-recovery relationships."- *Journal of Services Marketing*, Vol- 18, No- 2 & 3.

Sinha, P. K. and Banerjee, A. (2004), "Store choice behavior in an evolving market", *International Journal of Retail and Distribution Management*, Vol. 32, No. 10, pp. 482-494.

Strugnell, C. (1997), "Factor affecting consumer acceptance of chilled ready meals on the island of Ireland", *Hospitality, Tourism and Consumer Studies*, University of Vista at Jordan Town, UK.

Sukalakamala, Boyce J. B. (2005), "Customer perceptions for expectations and acceptance of an authentic dining experience in Thai restaurants", *Hospitality and Retailing (NHR)*, Texas Tech University, Lubbock, Tx 79409, USA.

Swan and Combs (1976), "Product performance and consumer satisfaction: a new concept", *Journal of Marketing*, Vol. 40 (2), pp. 25-33.

Tarun K. S. and Chopra, S. L. (2007), "Beyond the retail hype", *Indian management*, pp. 12-27.

Vijayraghavan (2007), "Future group to focus on lifestyle and non grocery biz for higher margins", *The Economic Times*, February, pp. 4.

Yi, Y. (1991), "A critical review of customer satisfaction", *Review of Marketing* (1990), American Marketing Association, Chicago II, pp. 68-123.

Zillur Rahman (2005) "Service Quality: Gaps in the Indian Banking Industry" - *ICFAI Journal of Marketing Management*, Vol- IV, No- 1, Feb.